

THE NEED AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF STUDYING INFORMATION-CULTURAL THREATS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract: this article analyzes the need and theoretical foundations of researching information-cultural threats in the conditions of digital transformation, the theoretical-methodological foundations of socio-philosophical research of inter-ethnic harmony and solidarity in the conditions of information-cultural struggles.

Key words: information, informational-cultural threats, informational-religious threats, informational-psychological threats, secularism, international harmony, digital transformation, terrorism, nationalism, social cooperation.

In the conditions of digital transformation, the research of informational and cultural threats and the assessment of social relations on this basis are gaining relevance. The second half of the last century is recognized as a period of rapid, large-scale development of information systems and telecommunication technologies, their penetration into almost all aspects of life and human activities, as well as the globalization of the information space, which has influenced and continues to influence the entire world development. It is noteworthy that people's need for active information exchange within the country and outside the world is greatly increasing. Such a rapid development of the information field, the growth of its potential and opportunities, its wide use in various areas of public and state life, can be one of the important factors determining the development of humanity in the new XXI century.

It reflects the legal stage of the evolution of modern society characterized by the wide application of information technologies and the development of the global information environment in the context of digital transformation. The process of forming a new society is related to the correct understanding and rational use of the possibilities of information technologies.

The concept of "information" was introduced into scientific circulation in 1928 by the American scientist R. Hartley in order to define the criterion of quantitative measurement of information transmitted through technical communication channels. In Hozip, this term is used in different meanings. Information in some (household) cases is information about a certain thing or event given by people, sometimes (cybernetics) - an organized change, a

measure of the organization of a system, in other cases, it is understood to represent and reflect the various aspects of objects. In addition to the many confusions about the essence of information, this concept has not yet been given a clear, universally recognized definition, and sometimes it is even thought that such a definition cannot be given. For example, according to T. Stoner, "we do not know what information is, except that we live in a society that we call an information society" [1]. In addition, we try to clarify the essence of the concept of "information".

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "information" is defined as follows: Akborot - (Latin "information" - to explain, explain) is one of the main concepts of modern science and politics; It is information transmitted by people first orally, and later in written or other forms [2]. So, we can summarize the definitions of information as follows: it is a broad concept that includes information about all existing objects, beings, and processes. At the same time, information is information, messages, and news that are transmitted between people.

Today, the planning and management of information production and the improvement of the quality of economic development are of great importance for all spheres of our social life. Of course, this information has a positive side, but it also has a negative side, that is, a harmful side, which not only threatens human life and future, but also destroys the life of society. Considering these two sides of the issue, information can be divided into the following types: socially useful information and harmful information.

Socially useful information does great things such as development of society and people's happiness, enrichment and increase of labor productivity, ensuring peace, while harmful information is information aimed at disruption, destruction, derailment of society and people's lives, harming peace.

Currently, the concepts of "information threat" and "information attack" are widely used in scientific usage. If we pay attention to the etymology of these concepts, it can be concluded that they can be used as synonyms. In historical sources, the word "attack" is used more widely. In essence, the term "khuruji" is also found in the book "Temur's Tuzuklari" by Sohibqiron Amir Temur. That is, the writings titled "My fifth council during the invasion", "Sixth council during the invasion", "Seventh council during the invasion" describe how the Ghanim attacked and the measures taken against it. Sahibqiron, who has always chosen the path of enlightenment against ignorance, writes in one place: "I wanted to bend the people to my side with sweet words and sweet stories, and I advised

them to put out the burning fire (anger) in their bodies with the right water of action." I wanted to tame them in this way" [3]. Therefore, it is possible to know through such sources that the peace and tranquility of the country was attacked and the way to fight against it was also in that period.

An information attack or threat is a set of conditions and factors that threaten the vital interests of individuals, society and the state in the information field.

Security against information attacks is important in all areas. Epicurus described the concept of security in connection with the harmony of man and nature [4]. T. Hobbes sees security in two virtues: faith and law [5].

In modern literature, the concept of "security" is considered as a system of conditions and factors that limit the object's functions and develop on the basis of its internal laws [6]. Also, security is described as protection from conditions and factors that pose a threat to an individual or society [7]. It should be emphasized that many definitions given to the concept of "security" are criticized by scientists and practitioners. In our opinion, the main reason for the lack of clarity in many definitions is that the definition of the concept does not take into account risk, which is considered the dialectical opposite of security. It is the study of the causes of the occurrence of danger that allows us to give a more precise definition of the concept of "security". As stated by G.A. Atamanov, security, as its derivative, acquires meaning in connection with risk [8]. According to the author, "security" represents the state of the object in the presence of internal and external influences, which is related to the violation of the mechanism of vital existence of the system. It would not be appropriate for him to perceive any threat as a danger, security comes from overcoming danger.

The following can be cited as the main means of information influencing the person: - mass information communications: information systems, for example, television, radio, Internet, etc.; - literature: artistic, scientific-technical, political, special, etc.; - art: in various directions, at the same time promoting "popular culture" and others; - education and upbringing: pre-school, general secondary education schools, secondary special vocational and higher education, etc.; - personal communication.

Persuasive information is a conscious action of the information subject (source), which can act on the basis of a clearly defined goal, assuming the obligation to exert its influence on a specific social object (person, social group, public institution, etc.). The encouraging information can be positive or negative, for example, if the encouraging information is negative, its activity may conflict

with the interests of the object and derail it. These actions are overt or covert and affect the subject mentally.

Based on the above considerations, one can come to the following conclusion: security is the ability of the system to deal with threats, as well as the ability to achieve a high level of its development. In our opinion, security is the description of the existence of any object, the ability of this object to protect its own values, goals, interests, in other words, the fundamentals that ensure the existence of the system, against threatening forces.

One of the main trends of the globalization process is characterized by the intensification of information exchange, the transformation of information fields and spaces into specific ideological polygons. This factor can create certain risks, especially in the educational system. That's why data neutralization is important. Because, as we mentioned above, the problem of ensuring the state's information security is the main and integral part of ensuring national security, and information protection is becoming one of the primary issues of the state. In today's era, when the flow of information is spreading rapidly, the role of these sources is incomparable for everyone in interpersonal communication and information exchange, in obtaining information about events and incidents in other countries. After all, it is possible to be aware of any information and news in a short period of time only through information sources. Currently, the types of information sources and their role in human life are expanding, as a result of which, together with the positive impact on the educational process, it is passing its threat. Such a situation requires more attention and responsibility for the education of the younger generation.

References:

1. Стоуньер Т. Информационная революция: наука, экономика, технология. – М., 1993. – С.335.
2. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Volume 1. – Т.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2006. – -В. 19.
3. Timur's rules. / Translation from Persian by A. Soguni and H. Karomatov. - Т.: Literature and art publishing house named after G'Ghulam, 1996. -В. 24-28.
4. Мыслители Греции. От мифа к логике. – Москва: Эксмо-пресс, Харьков: Фолио, 1998. – С. 774.
5. Гоббс Т. Левиафан. – Москва: Мысль, 2001. – С. 396.
6. Заплатинський В. М. Терминологія науки о безпеки. Zbornik prispjevov zmedzinarodnej edeckeje konferencie «Bezhecnostna veda a bezpecnostne vzdelanie». –Liptovsky Mikulas: AOS v Liptovskom Mikulasi, 2006. – С.78-80.

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7. Дзлиев М.И., Романович А.Л., УрсулА.Д. Проблемы безопасности: теоретико-методологические аспекты. – Москва: МГУК, 2001. – С.9.
8. Атаманов Г. А. Информационная безопасность: сущность и содержание // Бизнес и безопасность в России. – 2007. – № 47. – С. 106.
9. Атаманов Г.А. Информационная безопасность в современном российском обществе: Социально-философский аспект: автореферат дис. ... кандидата философских наук. – Волгоград, 2006.
10. Begalov В.А. Econometric modeling of trends in the formation and development of the information and communications market: thesis. Autoref.... i.f.d. - Т.: TDIU, 2001.

